

QUESTIONNAIRE AND ITS APPLICATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7428151>

Abstract: Sociological research is a complex process. He's just a questionnaire although it seems like a simple request through, in fact, conducting a sociological study requires a serious approach. The preparation of questionnaires, the participation of respondents in the survey, the establishment of psychological contact with them, the preparation of the place of the survey, the distribution of questionnaires and the organization of such work as the collection of the questionnaire indicates the complexity of the organization.

For this reason, the researcher can use other forces and tools as auxiliary tools for the qualitative organization of research.

Keywords: research, survey method, questionnaire, interview, respondent, empirical research.

АНКЕТА И ЕЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ

Аннотация: Социологическое исследование – сложный процесс. Он просто анкета хотя это кажется простым запросом через, на самом деле проведение социологического исследования требует серьезного подхода. Подготовка анкет, участие респондентов в анкетировании установление с ними психологического контакта, подготовка места проведения анкетирования, раздача анкет и организация такой работы, как сбор анкеты свидетельствует о сложности организации.

По этой причине исследователь может использовать другие силы и инструменты в качестве вспомогательных средств для качественной организации исследования.

Ключевые слова: исследование, метод опроса, анкета, интервью, респондент, эмпирическое исследование.

ANKETA VA UNING QO‘LLANILISHI

Annotatsiya: sotsiologik tadqiqotlar murakkab jarayondir. Anketa garchi oddiy so‘rov bo‘lib tuyulsa-da, aslida sotsiologik tadqiqotlar o‘tkazish jiddiy yondashuvni talab qiladi. Anketalarni tayyorlash, respondentlarning so‘rovnomada ishtirok etishi ular bilan psixologik aloqani o‘rnatish, so‘rov o‘tkaziladigan joyni tayyorlash, anketalarni tarqatish va anketani yig‘ish kabi ishlarni tashkil etish tashkilotning murakkabligidan dalolat beradi.

Shu sababli, tadqiqotchi tadqiqotni sifatli tashkil etish uchun yordamchi vosita sifatida boshqa kuch va vositalardan foydalanishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: tadqiqot, so‘rov usuli, anketa, intervyu, respondent, empirik tadqiqot.

INTRODUCTION

Setting goals and objectives defines the object and subject of research leads to detection. The object of sociological research is various branches of social reality, reflecting the problem under study can be microprocessors. When determining the object of empirical research, it is necessary to proceed from the problem.

Any sociological research is connected with sociological knowledge, traditions and ensuring continuity and consistency of scientific schools is a syllable. In place of sociological knowledge in society, in combination with needs, it becomes richer, and in this aspect of sociological research methodology is also being improved. The empirical method of sociological research — research

aimed at the micro-processes of changing, mobile reality - is carried out by studying the actions, conditions, motives of a certain complex of individuals. A sociological method based on social concrete facts, consisting of initial sociological information, consists of an elementary amount of knowledge directly related to a person. This leads to increased subjectivism. This is especially true of the interrogation method" [1, 149].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A questionnaire is an expression of a system of questions capable of testing the hypothesis introduced, which interact with the general concept and direction of research to obtain empirical information. The main criterion for the organization of the questionnaire and the structure of the questions is clarity, the interpretation of the questions separately is an aspiration.

The word "questionnaire" is a French term used to refer to research, study, survey. As a rule, the questionnaire refers to a set of questions on a specific topic, which are answered by a group of people under study. The questionnaire is close to the interview genre in some properties, but the questions asked will be focused not on a single respondent, but on a large group of people, while structured questions are asked not orally, but in writing. The main components of the questionnaire form are the sociologist, the respondent and the questionnaire.

The introduction to the questionnaire sets out the scientific research or its group in which the sociologist conducts the research, the location of the scientific organization, the name and purpose of the research, the surname, title and degree of the questionnaire compiler, the time of the questionnaire and the method of answering the questions asked to the respondent, and finally, the methods and conciseness of submitting the completed questionnaire to whom and where. The importance of this introduction lies in the fact that the respondent usually gets the initial information from the introduction and has a preparatory spirit.

The second part reflects the respondent's specific passport. This implies the presence of questions concerning the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Often questions concerning the respondent's identity are given in the final part of the questionnaire. In this regard, some sociologists argue that if, on the one hand, asking questions about personality at the beginning of the questionnaire does not correspond to etiquette and ethics, on the other hand, such questions can intimidate the respondent and prevent him from getting objective and correct answers that serve a purpose.

RESULTS

The complex of personality issues may include issues related to gender, age, education, profession, social origin, party membership, marital status.

At the next stage, questions related to establishing contact with the respondent are raised. The issues of building communication follow from the goals and objectives of the study. At the same time, such questions should not go beyond the norm, since exceeding such questions can reduce the level of responsible approach of the questionnaire to the main questions.

At the next stage, the main questions of the questionnaire should be asked in detail and in a logical connection. Key questions allow you to get important information about their content. The main questions of the questionnaire should be answered exhaustively about the goals and objectives of the research program.

The final stage of the questionnaire should include the final questions. Such questions should serve to lead respondents out of the situation of psycho-intellectual arousal, drawing conclusions on all the issues put forward at the basic stage.

In general, the questionnaire method has the following advantages:

a) respondents try to justify their point of view to some extent when answering;
b) using the questionnaire method, you can attract a huge number of people to the object of research;

c) with the help of polls, it is possible to notice trends in public opinion in a timely manner.

The questionnaire questions will consist of open, semi-open and closed options. Open-ended questions allow the respondent to think broadly, to act on the basis of detailed observation of the questions posed. At the same time, open-ended questions can create certain difficulties for the respondent, narrowing the range of answers.

The process of conducting a survey directly is an important stage that a sociologist should approach with the utmost seriousness. This process is called the request procedure and encourages you to comply with the following requirements:

a) the sociologist must arrive at the polling place in a timely manner and independently, together with the administrative management of the polling place and a representative of the community organization; when filling out the questionnaire, almost all invited persons must be present, be at a certain distance from each other (so as not to move and not interfere with each other);

b) the sociologist tells the audience about the purpose, content and significance of the research. It slowly explains how to fill out the questionnaire, for what purposes the results of the study are used, for unclear questions, you should contact only the sociologist himself, and not ask and answer each other the questionnaire questions.;

c) experience shows that in the collected cases, there are often cases when there are not enough pens, papers. For this reason, it does not hurt if the sociologist brings writing materials with him;

d) before distributing the questionnaires, the sociologist should ask people who do not fill out the questionnaire to leave the room.

DISCUSSION

"During the questionnaire survey, the respondent feels the content of the question and the way of presentation of the respondent should be transformed into everyday vocabulary. In addition, from the point of view of the volume of questions, some respondents have psychological characteristics: their awareness and cognition, it is advisable to adapt to memory and analytical abilities is considered. In our opinion, experienced marketers should listen to the following tips when composing questions:

- the questionnaire questions should be specific;
- answers to the question that require the form to be convenient for writing;
- the question should be asked only about one subject;
- the question should be as short and concise as possible, if the question is longer, then its true essence should be stated in understandable language;
- questions should give correct and accurate answers"[2, 144].

During the collection of questionnaires, the sociologist should check each questionnaire to determine the reasons, if there are unfilled questions, contact the respondent, explain if there are unclear questions, and try to get comprehensive answers to all questions.

In some cases, the questionnaire filler deliberately refuses to answer some questions, in such cases, the sociologist should write opposite such questions in the questionnaire that the respondent refused to answer. Sometimes the respondent expresses the idea to give a detailed answer to certain questions.

CONCLUSION

So, in the methodology of sociological research on continuous monitoring of public opinion, this is achieved through the use of query tools. The most important thing on the other hand, the survey tool is a sociological survey or questionnaire survey method.

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